

CAUSES AND PREVENTION FACTORS OF PEDAGOGICAL CONFLICTS IN PRIMARY CLASS TEACHING ACTIVITY

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Abstract: This article discusses the causes and prevention factors of pedagogical conflicts in the teacher's work during primary education.

Key words: Educational system, pedagogical conflict, primary education, teacher, ethics, Makhbub-ul-qulub.

"In the system of communication in the pedagogical process, the relationship between the teacher and the student occupies a large place. The teacher is the main figure, the leader in the pedagogical process. He is entrusted with the task of teaching and educating the young generation. The teacher showed self-sacrifice in pedagogic work, performed his duties as a teacher at a high level, imparted knowledge to children, was able to instill the light of honesty, beauty, truth, decency and morality into their hearts, and gained such prestige and respect. Unfortunately, the same cannot be said about all teachers. There are those who, with their careless behavior, discourage the child from reading and hurt his tongue inappropriately. There are many examples of this in pedagogical practice and fiction. Such people have a negative impact on the education of young people and their morals. They cause damage to educational work that is difficult to repair. As a result, a conflict arises between the teacher and the student.³⁸

Ethical norms related to the formation and upbringing of a perfect creative personality are expressed in pedagogical ethics. One of the conditions for having a positive influence on the student is the unity of the demands placed on him with confidence. This rule has been tested many times in pedagogical practice and has proven itself. The results of the interview with teachers and students show that, along with polite teachers, there are also teachers who treat children unnecessarily, yelling at them. Such treatment does not correspond to universal and national moral norms accepted in the society. Such teachers cannot gain respect among children.

The pedagogical process, the process of education, the nature of people are so complicated that the teacher is sometimes "forced" to do more, whether he wants to or not, and when the student does not fulfill the appropriate requirements of the teacher, he cannot control himself. The teacher considers his demands, even the situation of the majority, to be doing good to the child, because he believes that he is doing this in order to educate the child, guide him on the right path, and raise him to be a good person. Narratives in the chapter "Educational Impact Statement" of Saadi Shirazy's "Gulistan" (Tashkent, 1968), "About Teachers" in Alisher Navoi's "Mahbub-ul-Qulub", "About Teachers" comments expressed in his articles are consistent with our opinion.³⁹

³⁸ Khalikov A. Pedagogical skills (textbook). - T., 2011.

³⁹ Ibragimov.Kh., Yoldoshev U., etc. Pedagogical psychology (study guide). - T., 2007.

Such situations often occur in the process of dealing with a child who is difficult to educate. It should not be forgotten that such a child usually comes from an unhealthy family. A child may be a victim of a bad environment in the family. Experienced pedagogues emphasize that it is difficult to work and deal with a child who is difficult to educate, at the same time, they need human love, politeness, and attention, and it is necessary to be tolerant, patient, and forgiving towards such children. Everyone knows that a teacher cannot punish a child who is physically injured. A physical education teacher does not require a child with an injured leg to participate in a running competition. A child can sometimes come to school with a broken heart and soul. Do all teachers take this into account in the educational process? Considering that the child does not want to answer, does not want to prepare the lesson, there are many cases of making the same demands and treating the students the same. Sometimes the child is required to do things that he cannot do.

An accidental letter of the teacher - the thought that the students have about him as a result of the action can have a negative effect on the process of education and training, and complicate the work of the teacher. Such conflicts usually last for a long time.⁴⁰ As a result, conflicts arise between the teacher and the student. Dissatisfied with the teacher, the student walks away from him. In some cases, adults demand an apology from the child, saying that they are protecting the teacher, while the conflict was caused by the teacher's wrong behavior. At such a time, the value of the child is not taken into account.

In some cases, the child is entrusted with responsible work, and the child does not fulfill the tasks of adults, does not like them to limit his independence, and often has a negative attitude to the demands of adults. And in families where parents have not noticed that their son or daughter has grown up, they still consider them "young children", there are frequent conflicts and conflicts between teenagers and adults. First of all, it is necessary to pay constant attention to the child's behavior, to strictly and continuously guide his behavior, and also to do all this in such a way that the child does not feel the constant guardianship of adults even in small things. Especially at the age of teenagers, they respect demanding but fair teachers who take into account their new positions in their lives, do not consider them "small".

For older children, their interests are diverse. If these interests are properly nurtured, they can have a significant impact on the development of a teenager's abilities and inclinations. The teacher sometimes has disagreements with the students about work or personal matters. The student looks critically at the evaluations of others. That is the reason for the resentment and hesitation in his mood. Accidental success or praise from adults causes the child to overestimate himself, overconfidence, and pride. Even a temporary accidental failure can teach a child not to believe in his own strength, increase the feeling of hesitation, timidity, lack of courage and shyness. Therefore, the relationship of teachers and educators with children requires special tenderness. In adolescence, the risk of being labeled as weak, not independent, and small increases.

Laziness in treatment, demandingness, disrespect, treating students like young children, disregarding their right to express their independent opinions on issues that they think they understand well, doubting their strength and capabilities to achieve high results, usually dissatisfaction or creates other clearly expressed negative reactions, events.

⁴⁰ Malla Ochilov. The teacher is the architect of the heart. Tashkent, "Teacher". 2001 year. Pages 56-57.

Certain mistakes happen in the life of some teachers. Teachers (meaning young teachers) always praise the same students (who are mastering) and always blame others (who are not mastering). On top of that, those who don't master it are often and harshly reprimanded, usually compared to their classmates who have mastered it. They even invite students who learn less to answer.

In such a situation, students become dependent on each other, and a feeling of dissatisfaction with the teacher appears. He gives a "bad" grade to a student who has not mastered much, and on top of that, a few disheartening, bitter, sarcastic words are also said. Such a situation occurs in the life of many teachers, and the student will not forgive this mistake for life. The causes of conflicts are reflected in the behavior of each person in the group, the characteristics of the nation, people and region to which the person belongs.

Knowledge of the causes of pedagogical conflicts and their prevention develops pedagogical culture. In order not to create pedagogical conflicts, the teacher's pedagogical ability and skills play an important role in preventing conflicts and problems. To achieve success in teaching, every teacher needs to acquire pedagogical skills. In order for the pedagogical activity to be effective, the teacher must have the following types of abilities:

The ability to know. A teacher should have a strong knowledge of his specialty, always follow discoveries in the field of his subject.

The ability to explain - to be able to deliver educational material to students in an understandable way, to be able to explain problematic and controversial topics based on real life examples:

The ability to observe is to pay attention to observation, which is related to the ability to enter the inner world of the student, to understand the personality of the student and his temporary mental states.

In order for the teacher not to create conflicts during the educational process, it is necessary to pay attention to the age and individual characteristics of the student. If students of each group are treated according to their character and temperament, there will be no conflicts between the teacher and the students.

Conflict is the motive of opposites. Conflicts arise in groups and communities. A person's position in society, how he behaves, does not happen by itself without any reason. We will focus on the concept of motive to explain the implementation of the activity and the behavior of the person. Motive is a more specific concept, it refers to the reason that explains the presence of a person's inclination towards this or that behavior. Conflict is an example of a conflict motive. The famous German scientist Kurt Lewin admits that the problem of motives is based on conflict and opposition. For example, there is a course called "resistance of materials" at the technical university, and it is not easy for many to master this course and pass the test. Even before the course begins, young students have such an attitude towards the students of this course that, of course, this course is difficult. How many generations of students have such a situation, now the actions of a specific person after the beginning of the course of study are explained by specific motives, and for a diligent student, this subject, like other subjects, requires constant research, preparation of lessons on time, for another, a lazier student. For there is no lesson more difficult than this lesson. Compulsory education in the Republic of Uzbekistan. The following types of education are compulsory.

- ❖ *school education*
- ❖ *general secondary education*

❖ *secondary vocational education*

Pre-school education aims to form a child's personality in a healthy and mature way, prepared for studying at school. Primary education (grades 1-6) and general secondary education (grades 1-6) according to the stages of general secondary education. Primary education is aimed at improving the basics of knowledge and skills necessary for general secondary education.

The need for general secondary education knowledge is also a factor. He developed independent thinking, improved abilities and practical education skills. The pros and cons of conflict. The negative aspects of pedagogic disputes are the subjective approach to groups, which is another serious mistake in the evaluation of students' knowledge. This was reflected in the differences in the evaluation of different students for the same work for the same answer by the student. Pay attention to this situation. A student with low learning ability is answering on the blackboard, speaking unconvincingly and out of place. In such a case, what is the attitude of the teacher? He takes the student's words as a condition, puts a "two" on it and moves it to its place: "You" will never be a person, "Even if they teach you, it is useless honors that it is. Now let's look at another situation. In front of the blackboard, a good learner is not ready for the lesson today, he answers without confidence, the teacher leans on him a lot. In these situations, the negative aspects of the conflict are clearly visible.

The positive aspects of the conflict are that the pedagogue uses brainstorming methods in the educational process. In the method of brainstorming, questions with a difficult situation are thrown to the group. Due to disputes, conflicts, confrontations, the opinions of students are expanding even more.⁴¹

Working together to achieve a goal. In the field of education, we will achieve the goal. We must strive together. The employees who organize education are pedagogues, so with whom we should work together for effective implementation of education. A teacher is also education. It is necessary for him to know how to learn a subject and how to learn it, taking into account the age and mental characteristics of children, how to educate children, and the laws of the formation of a human personality.

Our society is wide-ranging and we can meet people of different characters there. Interpersonal conflicts are definitely manifested in activities. For example, we will see in the example of a group. Imagine we have talented individuals in one group. They are able to express their independent opinions by mastering each content well, and due to the wide range of opinions, conflicts, major disagreements and disputes arise between them. Each member of the group can prove the correctness of his opinion, in such cases, the teacher will manage the conflict. We can see conflicts between individuals in every field. If people work on themselves, if they can prove their point, they will also find a solution to conflicts.

Communication is a method of resolving and managing pedagogical conflicts. There are different forms of conflict in communication. For example, it is done face-to-face or by technical means (telephone, telegraph and similar means). There may be conflict between some members of the family. The main factor in avoiding conflict when starting a relationship is to get along and understand each other. It is necessary to be able to understand the complexity of this process, if necessary, to find a mutual understanding.⁴²

⁴¹ Achilov Malla. The teacher is the architect of the heart. - T., 2000.

⁴² Azizkhodjaeva N.N. Pedagogical technology and pedagogical skills (study guide). - T., 2006.

The teacher communicates with people - young children - who are just coming into life and are forming into full-fledged individuals. As a result of some random behavior of the teacher, the opinion of the students about him can have a negative effect on the educational process and complicate the work of the teacher. Usually, such disputes last a long time and are resolved in favor of the teacher. In order to protect the teacher's reputation, adults sometimes destroy the student's dignity and demand an apology from the student, although the reason for this conflict was the teacher's wrong behavior.

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